

MODELLING THE CRASH RESPONSE OF A COMPOSITE AIRFRAME SECTION

Alastair Johnson
German Aerospace Establishment (DLR)
Institute for Structures and Design
D-70569, Stuttgart, Germany

ABSTRACT

The paper describes the simulation of the dynamic crash response of a carbon fibre reinforced plastics (CFRP) airframe section using an explicit finite element (FE) analysis code. The calculated structural response is compared with results reported in [1] from a drop test on a Lear Fan 2100 fuselage section. Predicted failure modes and dynamic response agreed reasonably well with observed test results.

INTRODUCTION

Composite materials are now being used in primary aircraft structures, particularly in helicopters, light aircraft, commuter planes and sailplanes, because of advantages such as light weight, high static and fatigue strength and their formability into large integral shell structures. However materials such as carbon fibre/epoxy are inherently brittle and exhibit an elastic response up to failure with little or no plasticity. Thus before these materials are used more extensively in larger passenger carrying aircraft structures it is important to have tools for assessing the crashworthiness of such structures and to consider whether special energy absorbing substructures or seats are required to maintain occupant safety levels.

Conventional metallic airframes absorb crash energy through plastic hinge formation and the folding or collapse of shell and beam elements. Modern FE codes such as PAM-CRASH and LS-DYNA3D are able to model these effects and have been successfully applied to simulate the collapse of metal structures. The validity of such codes for modelling the crash response of composite structures has not been verified. Current crashworthiness studies on composite airframe structures are based on hybrid codes such as KRASH in which the dynamic properties of a composite element are tested and the measured load deflection response is used to define the spring stiffness characteristics for use in an idealised mass/spring model of the structure. Such techniques have been successfully applied to study the crashworthiness of composite fuselage sections in [1], but require extensive calibration tests on the structure and are thus not a fully predictive tool. In the work reported here the explicit FE code PAM-CRASH [2] is used to analyse the crash response of a CFRP fuselage section of the Lear Fan 2100 - an all composite commuter aircraft [3]. Computed responses are compared with structural tests carried out at NASA Langley Research Center and reported in [1] in which a Lear Fan fuselage section containing two frames was drop tested from a height of 4.6 m. The work reported here was carried out within a cooperation between the DLR and NASA.

The airframe section consists of a CFRP cylindrical shell stiffened by two CFRP frames. The stress-strain properties of the quasi-isotropic carbon fabric laminates were measured in tension and compression and used to provide data for a composite materials damage model implemented in PAM-CRASH, which was used in the FE calculations. A comparison with results from a quasi-static crush test on the section and the drop test results reported in [1] gives valuable information on the validity of FE models for composite aircraft structures under dynamic loads, and shows that in general the brittle nature of the materials is reflected in higher peak accelerations in the structure than in an equivalent aluminium section. Crash safety for composite structures thus requires attention to be paid to additional energy absorbing devices and substructures.

COMPOSITE AIRFRAME SECTION

STRUCTURAL DETAILS

Fig. 1 FE model of the Lear Fan fuselage half-section

The composite section modelled in the analysis consists of a short length of the Lear Fan 2100 fuselage containing two CFRP frames with CFRP skins, along with the longitudinal aluminium floor beams which support the two pairs of seat rails. This section was chosen because of its inclusion in a NASA test programme in which full scale crash tests are being carried out on composite airframes. As reported more fully in [1] and [4], NASA Langley Impact Dynamics Branch have purchased two complete Lear Fan aircraft in order to study the safety aspects of all composite bonded aircraft structures. Full details of the section geometry including photographs of the test section are given in [1]. The FE geometry half-model shown in Fig. 1 shows the essentials of the structure. It consists of an oval shell with maximum diameter 1.54 m, 0.3 m in length, containing two frames 0.14 m apart. The frames are fabricated as 'Z' profiles 50 mm deep with a 25 mm flange which are bonded to the shell thus giving an 'L' stiffener. At the base of the section the frame doublers are about 100 mm in height where they are attached to four longitudinal floor beams which support the seat rails in pairs. The seat rails are attached to the frames and stiffened laterally and vertically by 'L' section beams or bulkheads.

The floor beams are aluminium plates with depths 180 mm (inner) and 128 mm (outer). The remainder of the structure consists of carbon fabric/epoxy laminates with a quasi-isotropic layup. Each composite ply is based on 8 harness satin weave carbon fabric in a Fiberite 934 epoxy resin with a nominal ply thickness of 0.33 mm. Considerable information on the Lear Fan composite structure, the materials used and the fabrication methods is given in [3]. The frames and bulkheads were bonded to the aluminium floor beams and the fuselage shell with epoxy adhesive. Layup details are:

Fuselage skin:	4 plies carbon fabric/epoxy laminate [45,0,0,45]
Frames and bulkheads:	8 plies carbon fabric/epoxy laminate [45,0,0,45] _s
Floor beams:	1.1 mm aluminium sheet.

The test programme on this particular section reported in [1] consisted of a quasi-static crush test of the lower part of the section, in which the seat rails were loaded vertically downward in a displacement controlled test to determine their load-displacement response. The results were used in hybrid code analyses reported in [1] to calibrate the response of the nonlinear beam elements used. The main dynamic test consisted of a section drop test onto a rigid floor from a height of 4.6 m giving an impact velocity of 9.2 m/s. Of particular interest is the deceleration as seen by an occupant on impact. In the test 45.4 kg masses to simulate the mass of an occupant were added to the seat pans, which were attached by very stiff aluminium plates to the seat rails. These are not shown in the FE model geometry in Fig. 1. The section was instrumented to measure floor and occupant decelerations during impact. PAM-Crash is an explicit FE code which is not appropriate for slow loading situations. The quasi-static crush test was simulated by applying a velocity of 3 m/s to the seat rails. Since the structural mass of the section is only 5.5 kg, inertia effects are small at this velocity, hence it is possible to simulate the quasi-static loading response. For the analysis of the drop test the seat rails are rigidly connected to a point 300 mm above the rails at which the 45.4 kg mass is added. The acceleration response at this point is then computed for comparison with test data. In addition to the composite section, a drop test simulation was also carried out for an all aluminium section with the same geometry and wall thicknesses. This gives some information on the different dynamic behaviour to be expected from composite in comparison with traditional aluminium aircraft constructions.

COMPOSITE MATERIALS PROPERTIES

In the analyses reported here it was decided to model the quasi-isotropic CFRP laminate as a single orthotropic material, rather than as a 4 or 8 ply laminate. Thus materials tests were carried out to measure the basic mechanical properties of an equivalent carbon fabric/epoxy laminated plate consisting of 8 fabric plies with a [45,0,0,45]_s layup, since no off-cuts from the actual section were available for materials testing. PAM-CRASH contains a layered shell element, thus a more detailed analysis of the structure can be carried out based on the properties of a single fabric ply. However, the former approach was preferred for these first analyses since the measured laminate failure properties should be more reliable than those predicted by a laminate analysis based on integration through the laminate thickness. Fig. 2 shows the stress-strain curves obtained in tension and compression coupon tests in a symmetry direction of the quasi-isotropic fabric laminate. Fig. 2 shows that the material has a higher E-modulus in tension than compression, with tensile strengths significantly higher than compressive strengths. The test curves were very reproducible and Table 1 summarises the measured properties of the materials based on one typical data set for each mode.

Both the tensile and compressive behaviour are nonlinear with a brittle failure mode. The tensile stress-strain curve is linearly elastic to a strain of about 0.6 %, at which there is a slight 'knee' probably corresponding to transverse fibre failure, followed by a slightly reduced slope. The compression curve is linearly elastic to about 0.25 % strain, at which the slope reduces with a very pronounced levelling off at about 0.5 % strain. This point is thought to be associated with

Fig. 2 Measured stress-strain properties of quasi-isotropic carbon fabric/epoxy

Fig. 3 Idealised stress-strain curve in composites damage model [5]

failure of the 0° fabric plies in compression, with the load being taken by the 45° plies before ultimate brittle failure. Thus the quasi-isotropic fabric laminates are approximately linearly elastic in tension, with a more nonlinear 'yielding' behaviour in compression. The material may be characterised as an elastic 'damaging' material. In Table 1, σ_i , ϵ_i refer to the failure stresses and failure strains in Fig. 1, whilst the subscript 'i' refers to the values at the end of the linearly elastic region where some initial microdamage takes place in the laminate causing the initial elastic modulus E_0 to be reduced. The remaining composite data required for the analysis, such as shear moduli, shear strengths and Poisson's ratios was calculated from laminate analysis, based on typical CFRP fabric ply properties. For the aluminium floor beams, elastic-plastic properties of a typical airframe aluminium alloy 2024 T351 were assumed, with initial modulus $E = 73.1$ GPa, tensile yield stress $\sigma_Y = 306$ MPa and yield strain $\epsilon_Y = 0.42$ %. The yield stress was then assumed to increase linearly with strain to a maximum value of 540 MPa.

Table 1 Measured properties and calculated damage parameters of quasi-isotropic carbon fabric/epoxy laminates

Modulus GPa	Stress MPa			Strain %			Damage	
	σ_i	σ_1	σ_u	ϵ_i	ϵ_1	ϵ_u	d_i	d_u
E_0								
Tension 54.5	327	502	30	0.6	0.94	1.1	0.02	0.95
Compression 45.0	112.5	209	57.4	0.25	0.67	0.85	0.31	0.85

PAM-CRASH contains several materials models and special elements for laminated composite materials, which are discussed in some detail in [5]. Most of these have been developed for unidirectionally reinforced laminates and have not been specifically validated for the fabric laminates of interest here. It was considered that a homogeneous orthotropic material with a linear volume damage function was the most appropriate model for the quasi-isotropic fabric laminate, as this model is applicable to brittle materials whose properties are degraded by microcracking. In the model it is assumed that the orthotropic stress-strain relation has the general form

$$\sigma = E \epsilon , \quad E = E_0 [1 - d(\epsilon)] ,$$

where σ , ϵ are the stress and strain tensors, E the stiffness matrix with initial values E_0 , and d is the scalar damage parameter which is a function of the first strain invariant or effective

volume strain ϵ , and which takes values $0 < d < 1$. Thus in this materials model all the material moduli are reduced linearly from their initial value as the damage parameter increases from zero. In the case of a bilinear damage function there are two damage constants d_1 and d_u to determine and the general uniaxial stress-strain curve has the general form shown in Fig. 3, where ϵ_u is a limiting strain above which the stress is assumed to take a constant value σ_u . The stress-strain curves in Fig. 2 are in this general form and can be used to calibrate the materials model and to determine the damage parameters d_1 and d_u for the analysis. The damage parameters may differ in tension and compression and the appropriate values measured from the curves are given in Table 1. In the FE analysis the tensile values are used when the effective strain $\epsilon > 0$, and the compressive values when $\epsilon < 0$. The parameter d_1 measures the departure from linearity at the first knee in the curves, and is thus small in tension, whilst the parameter d_u determines how quickly the stress falls from its peak value to the assumed small residual value σ_u . For the FE analysis it is not good practice to reduce the material stresses directly to zero as in Fig. 1, as this may lead to numerical instabilities. Thus ϵ_u is chosen to be a little above the measured fracture strain, and d_u has a value close to unity indicating that the material is nearly fully damaged.

Fig. 4 Crush behaviour of composite subfloor section - comparison of test results (upper [1]) with FE simulation (lower)

FE MODEL AND RESULTS

Fig. 1 shows the FE geometry of the half frame structure, which was assumed to behave symmetrically about its mid-plane. The structure is modelled by 4-node Mindlin shell elements, and contains about 2500 elements with 3035 nodes, each having 6 degrees of freedom. The fuselage shell was modelled as a single ply of the orthotropic elastic damaging material with the materials data given in Table 1. The frames, frame doublers and bulkheads were modelled as a simple laminate with two plies of the orthotropic elastic damaging material, and the floor beams as isotropic elastic-plastic plates with the aluminium data given above. The analysis was carried out with PAM-CRASH [2], an explicit FE code specially developed for structural impact and crash simulations.

Fig. 4 shows predicted load-deflection behaviour computed at the seat rails for the quasi-static crushing load case discussed above. This may be compared with the response measured by NASA and reported in detail in [1]. The shapes of the predicted and measured curves show a remarkable similarity, and study of the computed damage parameter during load application supports the observed failure sequence recorded on the NASA test results. However, the predicted loads are seen to be generally above the test values. The reason for this is thought to be because the tests were carried out on the lower part of a section cut off at the floor level, whereas the analysis refers to the complete structure shown in Fig. 1, which is thus much stiffer. Further analyses are being carried out to investigate this effect in more detail.

Fig. 5 Acceleration response at seat in drop test - comparison of FE simulations for composite and aluminium sections with filtered test results [1]

Figs. 5 summarises the results for the seat pan accelerations for the drop test analysis on the composite fuselage section, an equivalent aluminium section, and the NASA test results as reported in [1]. Note that the test results are strongly filtered. The composite section analysis shows a strong, narrow 200 g peak at about 2 ms. which is absent in the test results shown, thereafter above 4 ms there is reasonable correlation with the test data, which has accelerations

generally a little higher than predicted. However, study of the unfiltered test data reported in [1] does indicate a 65 g pulse at about 2 ms which was filtered out of the test data plotted in Fig. 5. Comparison with the computed aluminium seat pulse is interesting. Here the initial high pulse is broader, but after 10 ms the aluminium section response has much lower accelerations than the computed and measured composite section response. After 12 ms the aluminium section has in fact rebounded from the rigid floor. Whilst the aluminium section has higher accelerations than the composite section for the first 10 ms, the composite section sees a broader pulse of 25 - 40 g for a duration of about 30 ms. Fig. 6 shows computed deformations in the two sections at 20 ms. The differences are significant showing that the FEA is sensitive to the different failure models being used, the stiffnesses of the quasi-isotropic composite material and aluminium being similar. After 20 ms the aluminium section is rebounding with some plastic deformation apparent mainly in the floor beams and the frame doublers. In contrast the composite structure is severely damaged, as would be expected from its brittle material response and low failure strains. Study of the damage parameter values in the deformed state indicates that the frame doubler is badly damaged and the bulkheads fractured. As a result there is extensive plastic hinge formation in the aluminium floor beams. Thus it would appear that the aluminium section remains integral, which allows it to rebound, whilst the composite section is heavily damaged in the contact region which prevents rebound.

Fig. 6 FE simulations of drop test - deformed geometry at 20 ms.

CONCLUDING REMARKS

The analyses carried out and the comparison with test data show that explicit FE codes such as PAM-CRASH are valuable tools for studying the crash behaviour of composite airframe structures. The software appears to be robust enough to handle brittle materials and the damaging materials model described in [5] seems to be suitable for modelling fabric reinforced laminates. A numerical comparison of a brittle composite section with a ductile aluminium section in a crash test confirms that the composite section is more severely damaged, with a higher peak accelerations and a broader acceleration pulse. Thus more attention needs to be given to occupant safety in composite aircraft structures. In the case of the airframe section studied here, this may be achieved by better design of the floor beams which support the seat rails, for example by using specially designed composite sine wave beam structures [6]. Such energy absorbing devices to replace the aluminium plate floor beams in the Lear Fan fuselage are under consideration in ongoing work at NASA as reported in [4].

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